

J β -CLOSED SETS IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Hamant Kumar

Department of Mathematics

Veerangana Avantibai Government Degree College,
Atrauli, Aligarh, U. P. (India)

Abstract: In this paper, a new class of sets called J β -closed sets is introduced and its properties are studied. The relationships among closed, α -closed, β -closed and their generalized closed sets are investigated. Several examples are provided to illustrate the behavior of these new class of sets.

2010 AMS Subject Classification: 54A05, 54C08

Keywords: β -closed, J β -closed, g β -closed and rg β -closed sets.

1. Introduction

Many investigations related to generalized closed and open sets have been published in various forms of open and closed sets. In 1937, Stone [13] introduced the notion of regular open sets. In 1965, Njastad [9] introduced the concept of α -open sets. In 1968, the notion of π -open sets were introduced by Zaitsev [20] which are weaker form of regular open sets in topological spaces. Velicko [18] proposed δ -open sets which are stronger than open sets. In 1970, Levine [5] initiated the study of so called generalized closed (briefly g-closed) sets. In 1983, Abd EI-Monsef et al [1] introduced the notion of β -open sets. In 1993, Palaniappan and Rao [10] introduced the concept of rg β -closed sets. Maki et. al [7] introduced the notion of g α -closed sets. In 1994, Maki et. al [6] introduced the notion of α g-closed sets. In 1995, Dontchev [2] introduced the notion of g β -closed sets. In 1996, Dontchev [3] introduced the notion of δ g-closed sets. In 2000, Veera Kumar [15] introduced the notion of g*-closed and \hat{g} -closed sets. In 2003, Veera Kumar [16, 17] introduced the notion of g $\#$ -closed sets. In 2008, Jafari [4] introduced the notion of *g-closed sets. In 2010, Viswanathan [19] introduced the notion of g* α -closed sets. Sarsak and Rajesh [12] introduced the concept of π g β -closed sets. In 2012, Sudha [14] introduced the notion of δ g*-closed sets. In 2016, Pious [11] introduced the notion of regular*-open sets. In 2019, Meenakshi et. al [8] have introduced a class of new sets namely η^* -open sets which is placed between the classes of δ -open and open sets.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X, Y and Z) always mean topological spaces. Let A be a subset of a space X. The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** [13] (resp. **regular closed** [13]) if $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ (resp. $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open** [20]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed** [20].

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

(i) **α -open** [9] if $A \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(A)))$.

(ii) **β -open [1]** if $A \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(A)))$.

The complement of a α -open (resp. β -open) set is called **α -closed** (resp. **β -closed**). The intersection of all α -closed (resp. β -closed) sets containing A , is called **α -closure** (resp. **β -closure**) of A , and is denoted by **$\alpha\text{-cl}(A)$** (resp. **$\beta\text{-cl}(A)$**). A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **clopen** if it is both open and closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

Definition 2.2. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [5] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.

The **generalized closure** of A is defined as the intersection of all g-closed sets in X containing A and is denoted by **$\text{cl}^*(A)$** . The **generalized interior** of A is defined as the union of all g-open sets in X contained in A and is denoted by **$\text{int}^*(A)$** .

Definition 2.4. The **δ -interior** of a subset A of X is the union of all regular open sets of X contained in A and is denoted by **$\delta\text{-int}(A)$** . The subset A is called **δ -open [18]** if $\delta\text{-int}(A) = A$. i.e. a set is δ -open if it is the union of regular open sets, the complement of a δ -open set is called **δ -closed**. Alternatively, a set $A \subset X$ is δ -closed if $A = \delta\text{-cl}(A)$, where $\delta\text{-cl}(A)$ is the intersection of all regular closed sets of (X, \mathfrak{T}) containing A .

Definition 2.5. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space. A subset A of (X, \mathfrak{T}) is called **regular*-open [11]** (or **r*-open**) if $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}^*(A))$. The complement of a regular*-open set is called **regular*-closed**. The union of all regular*-open sets of X contained in A is called **regular*-interior** and is denoted by **$\text{r}^*\text{-int}(A)$** . The intersection of all regular*-closed sets of X containing A is called **regular*-closure** is denoted by **$\text{r}^*\text{-cl}(A)$** .

Definition 2.6. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is called **η^* -open [8]** set if it is a union of regular*-open sets (r*-open sets). The complement of a η^* -open set is called **η^* -closed**. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is called **η^* -Interior** of A is the union of all η^* -open sets of X contained in A and is denoted by **$\eta^*\text{-int}(A)$** . The intersection of all η^* -closed sets of X containing A is called as the **η^* -closure** of A and is denoted by **$\eta^*\text{-cl}(A)$** .

Remark 2.7.

- (i) regular open $\Rightarrow \pi$ -open $\Rightarrow \delta$ -open $\Rightarrow \eta^*$ -open \Rightarrow open $\Rightarrow \alpha$ -open \Rightarrow s-open $\Rightarrow \beta$ -open
- (ii) regular closed $\Rightarrow \pi$ -closed $\Rightarrow \delta$ -closed $\Rightarrow \eta^*$ -closed \Rightarrow closed $\Rightarrow \alpha$ -closed \Rightarrow s-closed $\Rightarrow \beta$ -closed
- (iii) regular open $\Rightarrow \pi$ -open $\Rightarrow \delta$ -open $\Rightarrow \eta^*$ -open \Rightarrow open $\Rightarrow \alpha$ -open \Rightarrow p-open $\Rightarrow \beta$ -open
- (iv) regular closed $\Rightarrow \pi$ -closed $\Rightarrow \delta$ -closed $\Rightarrow \eta^*$ -closed \Rightarrow closed $\Rightarrow \alpha$ -closed \Rightarrow p-closed $\Rightarrow \beta$ -closed

Remark 2.8. For every subset U of X ,

- (i) $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{s-cl}(U) \subset \alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset \eta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset \delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \pi\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{r-cl}(U)$.
- (ii) $\text{g-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset \eta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset \delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \pi\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{r-cl}(U)$.
- (iii) $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{p-cl}(U) \subset \alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset \eta^*\text{-cl}(U) \subset \delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \pi\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{r-cl}(U)$.

Definition 2.9. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (1) **δ -generalized closed** (briefly **$\delta\text{g-closed}$**) [3] if $\delta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (2) **$\text{g}\beta$ -closed [2]** if $\beta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (3) **α -generalized closed** (briefly **$\alpha\text{g-closed}$**) [6] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (4) **δg^* -closed [14]** if $\delta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is g-open in X .
- (5) **generalized α -closed** (briefly **$\text{g}\alpha$ -closed**) [7] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is α -open in X .
- (6) **generalized* α -closed** (briefly **$\text{g}^*\alpha$ -closed**) [19] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\text{g}\alpha$ -open in X .
- (7) **$\hat{\text{g}}$ -closed [16]** if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is semi-open in X .
- (8) ***g-closed [4]** if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\hat{\text{g}}$ -open in X .
- (9) **g^* -closed [15]** if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is g-open in X .
- (10) **$\text{g}^\#$ -closed [17]** if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is αg -open in X .

- (11) $\pi g\beta$ -closed [12] if $\beta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (12) $rg\beta$ -closed [10] if $\beta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .
- (13) g -open (resp. δg -open, $g\beta$ -open, αg -open, δg^* -open, $g\alpha$ -open, $g^*\alpha$ -open, \hat{g} -open, $*g$ -open, g^* -open, $g^\#$ -open, $\pi g\beta$ -open, $rg\beta$ -open) set if the complement of A is g -closed (resp. δg -closed, $g\beta$ -closed, αg -closed, δg^* -closed, $g\alpha$ -closed, $g^*\alpha$ -closed, \hat{g} -closed, $*g$ -closed, g^* -closed, $g^\#$ -closed, $\pi g\beta$ -closed, $rg\beta$ -closed).

3. $J\beta$ -closed Sets

In this section a new class of generalized closed sets, called $J\beta$ -closed sets are introduced. The relations between $J\beta$ -closed sets and various existing closed sets are investigated.

3.1 Definition A subset U of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **$J\beta$ -closed** if $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$ whenever $U \subset M$ and M is η^* -open in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.2 Proposition. Every g -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a g -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is open, so M is open. Given that U is g -closed, $\text{cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset M$, which implies that U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.3 Proposition. Every g^* -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a g^* -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is g -open, so M is g -open. Given that U is g^* -closed, $\text{cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset M$, which implies that U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.4 Proposition. Every δ -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a δ -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since U is δ -closed, $\delta\text{-cl}(U) = U \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$ and hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.5 Proposition. Every δg -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a δg -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is open, so M is open. Given that U is δg -closed, $\delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.6 Proposition. Every δg^* -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a δg^* -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is g -open, so M is g -open. Given that U is δg^* -closed, $\delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \delta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.7 Proposition. Every αg -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a αg -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is open, so M is open. Given that U is αg -closed, $\alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.8 Proposition. Every $g\alpha$ -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $g\alpha$ -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is α -open, so M is α -open. Given that U is $g\alpha$ -closed, $\alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.9 Proposition. Every $g\alpha^*$ -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $g\alpha^*$ -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is $g\alpha$ -open, so M is $g\alpha$ -open. Given that U is $g\alpha^*$ -closed, $\alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.10 Proposition. Every $g^\#$ -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $g^\#$ -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is αg -open, so M is αg -open. Given that U is $g^\#$ -closed, $\text{cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.11 Proposition. Every $*g$ -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $*g$ -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is \hat{g} -open, so M is \hat{g} -open. Given that U is $*g$ -closed, $\text{cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.12 Proposition. Every \hat{g} -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a \hat{g} -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is s -open, so M is s -open. Given that U is \hat{g} -closed, $\text{cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.13 Proposition. Every $g^*\alpha$ -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $g^*\alpha$ -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is $g\alpha$ -open, so M is $g\alpha$ -open. Given that U is $g^*\alpha$ -closed, $\alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. As $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset \alpha\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. We get $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.14 Proposition. Every $g\beta$ -closed set is $J\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $g\beta$ -closed set and M be any η^* -open set containing U in X . Since every η^* -open set is open, so M is open. Given that U is $g\beta$ -closed, $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $J\beta$ -closed.

3.15 Proposition. Every $J\beta$ -closed set is $\pi g\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $J\beta$ -closed set and M be any π -open set containing U in X . Since every π -open set is η^* -open, so M is η^* -open. Given that U is $\pi g\beta$ -closed, $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $\pi g\beta$ -closed.

3.16 Proposition. Every $J\beta$ -closed set is $rg\beta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let U be a $J\beta$ -closed set and M be any r -open set containing U in X . Since every r -open set is η^* -open, so M is η^* -open. Given that U is $J\beta$ -closed, $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence U is $rg\beta$ -closed.

3.17 Remark. From the above definitions, theorems and known results the relationship between $J\beta$ -closed sets and some other existing generalized closed sets are implemented in the following figure:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

3.18 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not g -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.19 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{b\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not δ -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.20 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not δg^* -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.21 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{b\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not δg -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.22 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a, b\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not $g\alpha^*$ -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.23 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{b\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not $g^\#$ -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.24 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not *g -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.25 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not \hat{g} -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.26 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a, b\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not $g^*\alpha$ -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.27 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a, b\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not $g\alpha$ -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.28 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{a, c\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not αg -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

3.29 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then the subset $A = \{b\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed but not g^* -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

4. Properties of $J\beta$ -closed sets

4.1 Theorem. The finite union of $J\beta$ -closed sets is $J\beta$ -closed.

Proof. Let $\{U_i / i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ be a finite class of $J\beta$ -closed sets of (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Let $U = \cup_{i=1}^n U_i$. Let M be a η^* -open set containing U . This implies $U_i \subset M$ for every i . By assumption $\beta\text{-cl}(U_i) \subset M$ for every i . This implies $\cup_{i=1}^n \beta\text{-cl}(U_i) \subset M$. Then $\beta\text{-cl}(\cup_{i=1}^n (U_i)) \subset M$. Thus $\beta\text{-cl}(U) \subset M$. Hence finite union of $J\beta$ -closed sets is $J\beta$ -closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

4.2 Remark. The intersection of two $J\beta$ -closed sets need not be $J\beta$ -closed.

4.3 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}\}$. Here $J\beta$ -closed sets are $\{\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. Then $\{a, c\} \cap \{a, b\} = \{a\}$ is not a $J\beta$ -closed set.

4.4 Theorem. For $x \in X$, then the set $X - \{x\}$ is $J\beta$ -closed or η^* -open.

Proof. Assume that $X - \{x\}$ is not η^* -open. So X is the only η^* -open set containing $X - \{x\}$. That is $\beta\text{-cl}(X - \{x\}) \subset X$. Then $X - \{x\}$ is a $J\beta$ -closed set in X .

4.5 Theorem. The subset S of X is $J\beta$ -closed in X if and only if $\beta\text{-cl}(S) - S$ contains no non empty η^* -closed set in X .

Proof. Necessity: Let F be a η^* -closed set in X such that $F \subset \beta\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Then $A \subset X - F$. Since A is a $J\beta$ -closed set and $X - F$ is η^* -open then $\beta\text{-cl}(A) \subset X - F$. (i.e $F \subset X - \beta\text{-cl}(A)$). Then $F \subset (X - \beta\text{-cl}(A)) \cap \beta\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Therefore $F = \phi$.

Sufficiency: Let us assume that $\beta\text{-cl}(A) - A$ contains no non empty η^* -closed set. Let $A \subset U$ and U be η^* -open. Suppose that $\beta\text{-cl}(A)$ is not contained in U , then $\beta\text{-cl}(A) \cap U^c$ is non empty η^* -closed set of $\beta\text{-cl}(A) - A$ which is a contradiction. Therefore $\beta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is a $J\beta$ -closed set.

4.6 Theorem. If M is $J\beta$ -closed set in X and $M \subset N \subset \beta\text{-cl}(M)$, then N is $J\beta$ -closed set in X .

Proof. Let U be a η^* -open set in X , since M is $J\beta$ -closed, we have $\beta\text{-cl}(M) \subset U$. Let $M \subset N \subset \beta\text{-cl}(M) \subset U$. Since $N \subset \beta\text{-cl}(M)$, we have $\beta\text{-cl}(N) \subset \beta\text{-cl}(M)$. Then $\beta\text{-cl}(N) - N \subset \beta\text{-cl}(M) - M \subset U$. By the above theorem $\beta\text{-cl}(M) - M$ contains no non empty η^* -closed set in X . Therefore $\beta\text{-cl}(N) - N$ contains no non empty η^* -closed set in X . Hence N is a $J\beta$ -closed set in X .

4.7 Theorem. Let D be a $J\beta$ -closed set in (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Then D is β -closed if and only if $\beta\text{-cl}(D) - D$ is η^* -closed.

Proof. (Necessity): Let D be a β -closed set in X . Then $\beta\text{-cl}(D) = D$ and therefore $\beta\text{-cl}(D) - D = \phi$ which is a η^* -closed.

(Sufficiency): Let $\beta\text{-cl}(D) - D$ be a η^* -closed set. Since D is $J\beta$ -closed, By theorem $\beta\text{-cl}(D) - D$ does not contain a non-empty η^* -closed set which implies $\beta\text{-cl}(D) - D = \phi$. That is $\beta\text{-cl}(D) = D$. Hence D is β -closed.

4.8 Definition. Let $B \subset A \subset X$. Then B is $J\beta$ -closed relative to A if $\beta\text{-cl}_A(B) \subset M$, whenever $B \subset M$, M is η^* -open in A .

4.9 Theorem. Let $B \subset A \subset X$. and suppose that B is $J\beta$ -closed in X , then B is $J\beta$ -closed relative to A . The converse is true if A is β -closed in X .

Proof. Suppose that B is $J\beta$ -closed in X . Let $B \subset M$, M is η^* -open in A . Since M is η^* -open in A , $M = V \cap A$, where V is η^* -open in X . Hence $B \subset M \subset V$. Since B is $J\beta$ -closed in X , $\beta\text{-cl}_A(B) \subset M$. Hence $\beta\text{-cl}_A(B) \cap A \subset V \cap A$ which in turn implies that $\beta\text{-cl}_A(B) \subset V \cap A = M$. Therefore B is $J\beta$ -closed relative to A .
 Now to prove the converse, assume that $B \subset A \subset X$ where A is β -closed in X and B is $J\beta$ -closed relative to A . Let $B \subset M$, M is η^* -open in X . Then $A \cap M$ is η^* -open in A by the definition of subspace topology. Since $B \subset A$ and $B \subset M$, $B \subset A \cap M$. Since B is $J\beta$ -closed relative to A , $\beta\text{-cl}_A(B) \subset A \cap M$. Since $B \subset A$, $\beta\text{-cl}(B) \subset \beta\text{-cl}(A)$. Hence $\beta\text{-cl}(B) \subset A$. Therefore $\beta\text{-cl}(B) \cap A \subset \beta\text{-cl}(B)$ which implies $\beta\text{-cl}_A(B) = \beta\text{-cl}(B)$. Hence $\beta\text{-cl}(B) \subset A \cap M = M$. Thus B is $J\beta$ -closed in X .

5. Conclusion

The concept of new closed set namely $J\beta$ -closed set using η^* -open sets is introduced and studied. The relationship of $J\beta$ -closed sets using existing closed sets is established. Finally, some of their fundamental properties are studied. Hence I conclude that the defined set forms a topology which results in this work may be entered widely. The $J\beta$ -closed set can be used to derive a new decomposition of unity, closed map and open map, homeomorphism, closure and interior and new separation axioms. This idea can be extended to bitopological and fuzzy topological spaces.

References

1. M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, S. N. EI-Deeb and R. A. Mahamoud, β -open and β -continuous mappings, Bull. Fac. Assut Univ. Sci., **12**, 77(1983).
2. J. Dontchev, On generalizing semi-pre-open sets, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Ser A. Math., Vol 16, (1995), 35-48..
3. J. Dontchev and M. Ganster., On δ -generalized closed sets and $T_{3/4}$ spaces, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ.math.,Vol. 17, (1996), 15-31.
4. S. Jafari, T. Noiri, N. Rajesh, and M. L. Thivagar, "Another generalization of closed sets", Kochi. J. Math. Vol. 3, (2008), 25-38.
5. N. Levine, Generalized closed sets in topology, Rend. Circ. Mat. Palermo (2), **19**(1970), 89-96.
6. H. Maki, K. Balachandran, and R. Devi, Associated topologies of generalized α -closed sets and α -generalized closed sets, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Ser. A. Math. 15 (1994), 51–63.
7. H. Maki, R. Devi and K. Balachandran, Generalized α -closed sets in topology, Bull. Fukuoka Univ. Ed., Part-III, 42(1993), 13-21.
8. P. L. Meenakshi, Unification of regular star open sets, International journal of research and analytical reviews, Vol. 6, Special Issue., (2019), 20-23..
9. O. Njastad, On some class of nearly open sets, Pacific. J. Math. , **15**(1965), 961-970.
10. N. Palaniappan, On regular generalized β -closed sets, Int. J. of Sci. and Eng. Research, Vol. 4, 4(1993), 1410-1415.
11. S. Pious Missier and M. Annalakshmi, Between Regular Open Sets and Open Sets, IJMA- Vol.7., No.5, (2016), 128-133.
12. M. S. Sarsak and N. Rajesh, π -generalized semi-preclosed sets, International Mathematical Forum, **5**(12), (2010), 573-578.
13. M. H. Stone, Application of the theory of boolean rings to general topology, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. 41 (1937), 375-481.
14. R. Sudha and K. Sivakamasundari, δg^* -closed sets in topological spaces, International Journal of Mathematical Archive, Vol. 3, No. 3., (2012), 1222-1230.
15. M. K. R. S. Veera Kumar, Between closed sets and g -closed sets, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Math., Vol 21., (2000), 1-19.
16. M. K. R. S. Veera Kumar, g^{\wedge} -closed sets in topological space", Bull. Allah. Math. Soc., Vol. 18, (2003), 99-112.
17. M. K. R. S. Veera Kumar, $g^{\#}$ -closed sets in topological spaces, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Ser A. Math., Vol. 24, (2003), 1-13.

18. N.V. Velicko, "H-closed topological spaces", Amer. Math. Soc. Transl., Vol. 78, (1968), 103-118,
19. A. Viswanathan, K. Ramasamy and R. Sudha, On $g^*\alpha$ -continuous functions in topological spaces, Journal of Indian Acad. Math, Vol. 32., No. 1., (2010), 45-58.
20. V. Zaitsev, On certain classes of topological spaces and their bicompatifications, Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR, **178**(1968), 778-779.

